

POLICY BRIEF

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THE RUSSIA-UKRAINE CRISIS: "THE RED LINES" AS FOUNDATIONS FOR MOSCOW'S ACTIONS.

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POLICY STATEMENT

The year 2022 started with the world's eyes turning towards Eastern Europe. The imminent threat of war between Russia and Ukraine carries several layers of actors and interests, encompassing economic, political, strategic, and having the capacity to overflow from the regional to the global scope. Still, it reverberates a clear message from Moscow about protecting its national security: move the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) away from its borders, shielding its territory. This Policy Brief seeks to shed light on Russia's policies and positions in the current crisis, analyzing it from Moscow's understanding of what it characterizes as its strategic surrounding's "red lines". Likewise, it seeks to clarify the atmosphere of "Russophobia" that hovers in the contemporary International System (IS).

BACKGROUND

Since the beginning of the 2000s, Russia has shown clear signs of repositioning in the IS. One can notice this movement, on the one hand, in normative terms and, on the other, in operational terms.

The first can be seen by the review and release of strategic documents (Military Doctrine, National Security Strategy, Foreign Policy Concept, Basic Principles for Nuclear Deterrence), which go along with Russia's positioning turn in the IS. Such documents reflect a sense of growing vulnerability to the country's security. Moscow is clear in interpreting IS instability as a product of the West's (namely, the United States) unwillingness and inability to share its dominant role in the face of a factually multipolar international order. Likewise, it is explicit in indicating the expansion of NATO to close to its borders - in what it considers its strategic surroundings, while a real threat to its national security.

The contribution of these threats to Russian sovereignty is symphonic with the Russian military technological advances and increments. In this sense, a gradual military reform expands the country's military capabilities, operationally supporting the normative content of the strategic documents and its positioning in the international arena. The country's military capabilities advances embody two main objectives: a) to ensure an effective second-attack capability; and b) to ensure response capabilities (conventional and nuclear) to conventional aggression.

Furthermore, it is accepted that the North-South amplitude of the country's Western border presents itself as central to Russia's Defense Policy. The finding permeates the analysis of the (un)enclosure situation of Russia's territory and the external security imperatives that limit its ability to act. The first refers to the geographic territorial imposition of the country, which causes isolation from the open world, hindering the logistics of commercial and military. The second encompasses advances by external powers and military infrastructure in its border surroundings, having as an inflection point the role of the advancement of NATO and Ballistic Missile Defense.

It is believed that the challenges imposed by US projects, beyond being answered in terms of the country's military capacity, encourage the formation of an external defensive line that forms an advanced security structure for the country.

FINDINGS

The creation of an external defensive line can be understood from the Kremlin's specification of "red lines". Putin quoted in November 2021: "We are constantly voicing our concerns about the 'red lines, but we understand that our partners – I must say the least – have a very superficial attitude towards all our warnings and talk about red lines". It is assumed, then, that the "red lines" to which Putin refers carry logics that permeate the political, strategic, and operational spheres.

Regarding the political sphere, Moscow shows constant concern with the advance of NATO around its borders. The list of demands presented by the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs as a way of peacefully resolving the current crises makes this clear: it wants the organization to go back to the positions of at least the end of the 1990s – demanding, for example, the withdrawal of Forces from Romania and Bulgaria. Likewise, it wants a signed commitment of Ukraine not joining the bloc.

The Kremlin seeks that NATO respects its tacit commitment not to expand near Russia's borders. Such commitment refers to the negotiations around the reunification of Germany at the time (Feb. 1990) the then US Secretary of State, James Baker, verbally assured the Soviet leader, Mikhail Gorbachev, that "the alliance would not move an inch to the East" if Germany could reunite within NATO. The Russians understood it as a gentleman's agreement, a commitment by Western peers that there would be no bloc's eastward expansion. A failure by Gorbachev not to code in writing, which Westerners take advantage of, claiming that there is nothing formally set out. Since its creation, NATO has gone through eight expansions, five of them in the post-Cold War. Of the 16 members states in 1991, it has grown to 30. Russia's borders are closely being approached, with Ukraine and Georgia having been nominated by the Bush administration to join the bloc at the Bucharest Summit in 2008.

Moreover, one might think: how paranoid Russia is in fear that NATO will attack. However, it is necessary to look to the not too distant past and investigate some somewhat controversial and questionable actions of the organization: the attack on Yugoslavia (1999), the invasion of Iraq (2003), the overthrow of the Libyan government (2011 - in apparent disregard for UN Security Council resolution 1973), where they used offensive means, violating their very status as a "defensive organization."

This political sphere, in turn, is intrinsically linked to the strategic sphere. Furthermore, here, attention is drawn to an aspect, sometimes not raised in the analysis: the nuclear issues. In terms of the strategic scope, it is necessary to remember that the entire deterrence system between major powers holding nuclear weapons - this date back to the Cold War - revolves around the maxim of "mutually assured destruction," which, institutionalized, embodies the concept of strategic stability. Nuclear nonaggression (first strike) is supported by the opponent's ability to retaliate (second strike) in equal destructive measure. However, this balance has some physical limitations: time - directly related to distance - and the technological advancement of weapon systems. Because the principle of mutually assured destruction ceases to work over short distances, and strategic stability ceases to exist when anti-ballistic missile defense systems are in operation.

Let us imagine that, hypothetically, Russia detects a massive attack against its territory at about 20min. This is enough time for an annihilating counterattack to be prepared and launched. If the attack is launched from a position very close to the territory, it may not have enough time to launch its response capability. So, every inch that NATO weapons systems advance east directly impacts the time-distance-retaliative capability relationship, impacting the validation of mutual containment logic. The NATO bases allocated in Eastern Europe (Poland and Romania) considerably shortened Moscow's response time. Going even further, considering here future bases to be allocated on Ukrainian territory in the face of Kyiv's accession to the bloc, Moscow's response capacity decreases drastically, making it unfeasible.

Furthermore, it is necessary to consider the technological advance in weapons systems, specifically the ballistic defense system (BMD). In partnership with NATO on European territory, the US project, signed to defend allies from possible missile attacks from Iran and North Korea, imposes severe limits on Moscow's second-strike capability. It should be noted that the progress of this project was only possible in the face of the US unilateral withdrawal from the ABM Treaty in 2001. Allies' involvement to use their territories as advanced bases and attack platforms – translated into the expansion of NATO to the Russian environment, highlights the indication of improper use of the alleged US "defensive" systems.

In operational terms, attention is drawn to several actions in the Russian environment that trigger the alert from Moscow: * the current authorization by the Ukrainian Parliament for the prolonged presence of US and NATO military personnel; * several military exercises taking place in Ukrainian territory: "Defender Europe" (the biggest in more than 20 years), Cossak Mace, Joint Endeavor, Rapid Trident, Sea Breeze (this one in the Black Sea). As well as the Steadfast Noon exercise carried out in a secret location - possibly in Italy - which simulated a nuclear war scenario.

CONCLUSIONS

In addition to tirelessly pointing to the Kremlin as the main responsible for the current level of crisis with Ukraine, it is crucial to take a step back and analyze related facts. Observing and reflecting on Moscow's "red lines" is nothing more than an exercise of understanding the other and its vision of the crisis. Furthermore, it is essential to note that, unlike what is advocated by Western liberal powers, the globalized world is still governed by real interests in security and sovereignty defense, which are willing to make use of state competition and the use of force as forceful tools when seeking to defend its interests. Overall, what seems to be an offensive move from Moscow could be stated as actions that seek to reduce the prevalence of NATO Forces in its surroundings and a response to US advances that threaten nuclear deterrence. For Moscow, it seems enough to be heard and to highlight its importance and interests in the contemporary international system. Nevertheless, it will be necessary to de-characterize Russia as an aggressor and take its interests and role as a power in the current World Order more seriously.

SUGGESTIONS

The suggestions raised here are more scenarios brought up in the face of an unfinished outcome of the current Russia-Ukraine crisis.

* Given Moscow's strategic findings, it is essential to consider how much this crisis may interfere in future negotiations of strategic stability treaties such as the "new START Treaty." The extension for another five years gives negotiators time. However, it does not seem to exempt a renewal that considers new technologies, including new nuclear and conventional strategic weapons systems. Likewise, it is questioned what the impacts of the crisis will be on possible future negotiation on European security agreements, such as a "reissue" of the Intermediate Nuclear Forces Treaty (INF – USA unilateral denounced in 2019).

* Will there be operational actions similar to the recently seen movements in Kazakhstan and, in the past, in Georgia, Kyrgyzstan, and Ukraine itself? Will Russia be surrounded by movements such as "Color Revolutions" with the motto of hybrid warfare, looking for destabilization on several fronts and further affront its "red lines"?

* In the face of a hypothetical Russian incursion, will the United States and its allies be willing to bear the costs of defending Ukraine? For how long will Germany be able to keep the pressure for a diplomatic solution, countering some of its NATO allies, to guarantee its energy supply through Nord Stream 2 pipeline?

* Moscow and Beijing show consonance in their position on the Ukraine crisis and the face of other threats in the IS. Beijing is against the inclusion of new members in NATO, indicating support for Moscow in case of new economic sanctions. Both governments are critical of the negative impact on peace and stability of the Asia-Pacific region caused by the United States, showing severe concerns about the AUKUS (Australia, the United Kingdom, and the US) defense alliance. China is on alert for Taiwan.

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